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The Impact of Collaboration among Vocational Teachers Implementing Teaching Practices During a State of Emergency

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Abstract

Collaboration has been an important factor for shaping the professionalism of vocational teachers (VTs) and in respect to this three profiles of VT emerge. Accordingly, highly collaborative VTs are open to educational changes, are self-confident in supporting student learning, use learner-centred teaching practices and develop their own professionalism more. However, it is not known how important VT collaboration was during the state of emergency and how it influenced their teaching. This paper aims to explain the nature of the collaboration between VTs during the state of emergency and its impact on the teaching practices implemented. The results revealed that the extent to which VTs participated in collaborative activities varied and collaborative VTs more often applied teaching practices that required better digital competences and these teaching practices enabled them to provide more feedback to the students as well as support their learning.

Keywords

Vocational teachers, professionalism, collaboration, teaching practices, state of emergency

1 Introduction

The first wave of the Covid-19 pandemic was announced worldwide at the beginning of 2020. Literally overnight all schools had to rearrange work according to a completely new situation. On 12 March, a state of emergency was declared in Estonia. Therefore, teaching in all schools and vocational education institutions was transferred to online learning. Schools had one day to reorganise their face-to-face teaching to online learning (Vabariigi Valitsus, 2020). This meant a new situation emerged for vocational teachers (VTs) overnight and required the rapid restructuring of existing activities and teaching practices, as well as acquiring the necessary digital competences for online learning, such as knowing and using the appropriate digital/virtual learning environments, tools, web applications for creating teaching materials, conducting lessons, giving feedback, interacting, communicating and collaborating (Vuorikari et al., 2022).

Therefore, digital competences which *involve the confident, critical and responsible use of, and engagement with, digital technologies for learning, at work, and for participation in society* (European Commission, 2019) became very important. Research has shown that some teachers had previously developed their own digital competences and were therefore in a slightly better position (Gudmundsdottir & Hathaway, 2020). However, most teachers lacked the experience and knowledge to teach in such an online mode (Delcker & Ifenthaler, 2020;

Gudmundsdottir & Hathaway, 2020). Teachers had to plan teaching differently and take into consideration circumstances that did not depend on them (Fahmalatif et al., 2021). Therefore, this rapidly changed situation caused uncertainty and teachers did not know which teaching and assessment methods were most relevant to choose (Gudmundsdottir & Hathaway, 2020).

To manage this new situation, teachers who had a higher level of digital competence provided help to their colleagues and became supporters (Delcker & Ifenthaler, 2020). Some teachers also sought help from their colleagues (Trust & Whalen, 2020). These activities enhanced teacher collaboration and helped them to cope more quickly with the situation and reduced the feelings of insecurity (Popa et al., 2020).

Research on change in vocational education and training (VET) has also shown that collaboration helped VTs to better adapt to change as well as supporting professional development (e.g. Runhaar et al., 2016; Sirk et al., 2020). In general, teacher collaboration is understood as interaction in a variety of activities (e.g. discussion about new and common norms, rules, values, teaching beliefs, goals, problem-solving together, creating new learning materials, planning teaching activities, sharing best practices etc.), which require common tasks in order to achieve objectives (Vangrieken et al., 2015). In Estonia, in the context of changes to VET (including reforms), based on Hoyle's (2008) professionalism model, where the scope of collaboration is an essential factor, three profiles of VTs have emerged (Sirk, 2020; Figure 1). Accordingly, VTs who collaborate more with colleagues in their school and outside, and with different business representatives develop their professionalism more, are better able to cope in changing situations and with new tasks and roles, as well as being able to perceive the change as part of their own professionalism (Figure 1). However, the most important factor is that collaborative teachers are also open to teaching innovations, use more learner-centred teaching practices and perceive their role in supporting as well cultivating their students (Sirk, 2020; Sirk et al., 2020).

Figure 1

Vocational teacher professionalism (Sirk, 2020)

However, the question arises of whether collaboration between VTs is also essential in rapidly changed situations for developing teaching practices that support student online learning.

The aim here is to explain the nature of collaboration between VTs during the state of emergency and its impact on the teaching practices implemented.

To achieve the aim, the following research questions are posed:

- How did vocational teachers differ in terms of their collaboration activities during the state of emergency?
- How did the collaboration activities of vocational teachers impact the teaching practices they implemented?

2 Methodology

To answer the research questions, the study theoretically relies on the model of VT professionalism focusing on collaboration as one important factor in managing change, including teaching innovation and professional development (Sirk, 2020). Second, quantitative analysis is conducted with data collected using a web-based questionnaire after the end of the

period of online learning required by the state of emergency. The number of completed questionnaires was 104. K-means cluster analysis was used to cluster VTs according to the forms of collaboration they engaged in. Using variance analysis, the clusters were described based on the teaching practices the VTs implemented.

3 Results

Based on the analysis, three clusters of VTs were identified (Table 1): 1) collaboration-detached (36%), 2) moderately collaborative (31%) and 3) frequently collaborative vocational teachers (33%).

Table 1
Clusters of VTs according to their collaboration activities

VT collaboration activities	M SD	cluster I	cluster II	cluster III	F	Sig
VTs discussed with colleagues of the same study group when planning the learning process <i>A seven-point scale ranging from 1 "definitely not" to 7 "yes, sure"</i>	<i>M</i> <i>SD</i>	1.42 ^{II and III}	3.67 ^{I and III}	6.24 ^{I and II}	542.93	0.00
Web-meetings and discussions with colleagues to share information/organise work <i>A four-point scale ranging from 1 "never" to 4 "very often"</i>	<i>M</i> <i>SD</i>	1.83 ^{II and III}	2.22 ^{I and III}	2.78 ^{I and II}	21.53	0.00
Collaborative lesson planning and teaching, and seeking feedback <i>A four-point scale ranging from 1 "never" to 4 "very often"</i>	<i>M</i> <i>SD</i>	1.59 ^{III}	1.92 ^{III}	2.43 ^{I and II}	19.16	0.00

Note. The mean difference is significance at the $p < 0.05$ level.

The clusters revealed that the extent to which VTs participated in collaborative activities during the state of emergency from Covid-19 varied, as emerged previously in the professionalism model (Sirk, 2020). The teachers in the third cluster evaluated that they often discussed with colleagues of the same study group when planning the learning process and participated in web-meetings to share information or organise work. In addition, they participated more often in collaborative lesson planning, teaching and seeking feedback from students, and in these activities they differed from the other clusters to a significant level (Table 1). They felt that collaboration between colleagues increased compared to the time before Covid-19. According to the frequency of their collaboration, it appears that they resemble the extensively networked professionals in the VT professionalism model (Figure 1).

The VTs in the first cluster evaluated their collaboration activities as the least frequent and clearly differ in this respect from VTs in the third cluster, as well from those in the second cluster. Therefore, they seem to resemble the collaboration-detached professionals in the model (Figure 1). They felt that their collaboration activities decreased during the Covid-19 period.

The second cluster of teachers is located between the first and third clusters according to their frequency of collaboration activities, like the school-centred professionals in the professionalism model (Figure 1), and interestingly, the frequency of their collaboration activities did not change compared with the time before Covid-19. They occasionally discussed with colleagues of the same study group when planning the learning process and seldom participated in the web-meetings and discussions with colleagues to share information or organise work. They rather seldom planned lessons collaboratively, but taught and sought

feedback more frequently than teachers in the first cluster but the difference was not at a significant level.

Analysing the emerged clusters of VTs in terms of their teaching practices revealed that they all implemented the following activities: often used discussion based on independently learned material, seldom differentiated teaching and assessment, often gave students tasks for independent learning from a textbook, workbook or the web, seldom guided students to write written works (reports, stories, essays), often created tasks using MS Word and other similar solutions and seldom guided students towards creative activities (manual activities, outdoor activities).

However, the clusters differed in terms of teaching practices which were more suitable for online learning, supported student learning and required a better level of digital competence. Accordingly, frequently collaborative VTs more often applied learning in pairs/groups and allowed students to compile assignments based on the learned material, while teachers in the other clusters engaged in these activities rather rarely. Therefore, the third cluster of teachers differ from the first cluster in terms of teaching activities at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. The third cluster of teachers most often sought feedback and supported student learning based on virtual learning environments (e.g. conducting lessons and personal communication via Zoom or GoogleMeets) and students with learning difficulties (carried out individual consultations or counselling, conducted lessons/consultations in a smaller group and individual meetings according to student progress). Other teachers implemented these practices less often and the difference compared to the first cluster of teachers was at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. In addition, teachers in the third cluster rather often implemented student-centred and integrated teaching and feedback via formal digital learning materials and channels and also allowed students to conduct more independent experiments, research and creative activities. Other teachers implemented these activities rather seldom and the difference between the third and the second cluster of teachers was at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. The results also showed that frequently collaborative VTs compared to the others more often used web applications for conducting teaching and providing feedback but the difference was not significant.

4 Conclusions

The results of the current study show that in the state of emergency, VTs that collaborate more with their colleagues also more often applied those teaching practices which required better digital competences and this coincides with a previous study which highlighted that more collaborative teachers have better technological skills (Vangrieken et al., 2015). Therefore, it can be concluded that increasing collaboration between teachers also supports more use of virtual learning environments as well as web applications. Furthermore, these teaching practices enabled frequently collaborative VTs to provide more feedback to their students, and support their learning, as well as those with learning difficulties.

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Biography

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